

Czechia

This report describes the structure of the national higher education system in Czechia, focusing on the institutional types as defined by national categories. It builds on the Eurydice Report on the national higher education system and complements it with quantitative information on the role of higher education institution (HEI) types in national systems, based on data derived from the European Tertiary Education Register (<http://www.eter-project.eu>) for the period 2011-2020.

Types of Higher Education Institutions

According to the Higher Education Act and the Education Act¹, there are four types of HEIs in Czechia:

- **Higher education institutions of university type** (*vysoká škola*)
- **Higher education institutions of non-university type** (*vyšší odborná škola*, tertiary professional schools)
- **Tertiary professional schools** (tertiary professional education)
- **Conservatories** (tertiary professional education)

It is important to note that only the first two HEI types, Higher education institutions of university type (offering educational levels ISCED 64, ISCED 74, ISCED 84) and the Higher education institutions of non-university type (educational levels ISCED 64, ISCED 74), are included in ETER. In contrast, Tertiary professional schools (offering ISCED 65 level) and Conservatories (offering ISCED 5 level, short cycle) are not covered by ETER. The type of a HEI is included in its statutes in accordance with the opinion of the Accreditation Bureau (previously the Accreditation Commission).

Higher education institutions of the **university type** may offer all three types of study programmes, Bachelor's, Master's and Doctoral degree programmes, and carry out scientific, research, developmental, artistic or other creative activities connected with these. Only higher education institutions of the university type can have the word university (*univerzita*) or its derivations in their name. Almost all public higher education institutions with the exception of two are the university type of institutions. Most of them offer study programmes from several educational areas, their faculties carry out research activities in various scientific fields.

Both state higher education institutions, the University of Defence (*Univerzita obrany*) and the Police Academy (*Policejní akademie*) are universities. The state military higher education institutions and the Police Academy have undergone transformations in terms of the content and organisation of education following Czechia's admission to NATO in 1999 and in compliance with international commitments to Interpol. Since 1 September 2004, the three existing military institutions have been merged into one – the University of Defence. Its establishment is regulated by legislation. Also, three private higher education institutions have recently achieved the university status: Jan Amos Komensky University Prague (*Univerzita Jana Ámose Komenského*)

¹<https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-education-systems/czechia/types-higher-education-institutions>

Praha), the Metropolitan University Prague (*Metropolitní univerzita Praha o.p.s.*) and the University of Finance and Administration (*Vysoká škola finanční a správní, a.s.*).

Higher education institutions of the **non-university type** (tertiary professional schools) offer mainly Bachelor's degree programmes and carry out research, art and other creative activities connected to the programme. They can also offer Master's degree programmes, if they receive accreditation for them, but they cannot realise Doctoral degree programmes. They are not divided into faculties. Admission requirements, study programmes, aims and content of education, methods, assessment and certification are the same as at higher education institutions of the university type.

Two public higher education institutions of the non-university type are transformed from previous tertiary professional schools – the College of Polytechnics Jihlava (*Vysoká škola polytechnická Jihlava*) and the Institute of Technology and Business in České Budějovice (*Vysoká škola technická a ekonomická v Českých Budějovicích*). All private higher education institutions started as institutions of the non-university type, only three of them became universities lately.

Main institutional characteristics. Legal status and the right to award a PhD

As stipulated by the Higher Education Act, the doctoral degree programmes are aimed at scientific research and independent creative activities in the area of research or development, or at independent theoretical and creative activities in the area of fine arts. All 28 higher education institutions of university type (University, *univerzita*) have the right to award PhDs. They are public institutions, with the exception of 2 private universities. Out of the 32 non-university HEIs, in 2020 there is 1 (private) PhD awarding institution.

Table 1 provides a quantitative overview of the main institutional characteristics of the 60 HEIs in Czechia by HEI type. All 28 higher education institutions of university type (University, *univerzita*) have the right to award PhDs. They are public institutions, with the exception of 2 private universities. Out of the 32 non-university HEIs, in 2020 there is 1 (private) PhD awarding institution.

Table 1. Institutional type and legal status by HEI type, 2020

Category		N	Public	Private	PhD awarding
Non-university	neuniverzitní	32	2	30	1

Category		N	Public	Private	PhD awarding
University	univerzitní	28	26	2	28
Total		60	28	32	29

Note: Numbers reflect inclusion of institutions in ETER

Institutional history. Older and younger institutional types

Data on the HEI foundation year provide information on the history of Czechia's higher education system and its evolution over time. While the Charles University (*Univerzita Karlova*), the oldest of today's universities in Czechia, founded in 1348, is among the oldest universities in Europe, only 9 other universities were founded before WW II, among them Palacký University in Olomouc (1573), the Czech Technical University in Prague (1707) and the Academy of Fine Arts in Prague (1799). Figure 1 shows that the expansion of the system in terms of the number of HEIs is relatively recent. The figure shows two separate phases of expansion of the HEI sector Czechia after WW II. In the first phase, the number of universities quickly increased after 1945 to 17 HEIs. From 1953 until 1991 no universities (existing in 2020) were newly founded. The second phase of expansion started in 1990, when the first tertiary professional school was founded (the Anglo-American University), and which comprised an expansion of both the university sector (until 2006), and the rapid growth of the (mostly private) non-university HEI sector, leading to 32 tertiary professional schools, exceeding Czech universities in 2020 in terms of the number of establishments.

Figure 1. Foundation year of HEIs by type

Students

With 90% of the students (ISCED5-7) enrolled in Universities, they are still the leading actor in the national higher education system. Complementarily, Non-university type HEIs enrol only 10% of the students. However, according to different institutional mandates, we also observe systematic differences between educational levels: Non-university type HEI account for about 13% of the bachelor students and 7.5% of master students. Accordingly, the universities enrol 87% of the bachelor and 92.5% of the master students in Czechia. The universities have a dominant, an almost exclusive, role in awarding PhDs (99.9% of the ISCED8 students are enrolled at universities).

Figure 2. Students by level and type of HEI, 2020

Note Total students include ISCED 5-7.

Personnel

People are a core resource for HEIs, as their competences are essential for teaching, undertaking research and producing scientific output. In that respect, ETER provides a rich set of data moving beyond the information available in EUROSTAT, which allows to analyse the composition of personnel by type of HEI.

As shown by Figure 3, there are major differences between Universities and Non-university type HEIs, as measured by total personnel in full time equivalents (FTE), and in the personnel composition.

With over 44,000 FTE, the 28 Universities account for over 97% of personnel in Czechia's higher education sector. As of the personnel composition, the share of support and administrative personnel is with 44% slightly higher at Universities than at Non-university type HEIs (41%). Research and teaching assistants (RTAs) play a limited role in Czech HEIs and account for only 3% of personnel at Universities and 6% at Non-university type HEIs. This category is mostly composed of PhD and master students supporting research and teaching activities reflecting the different extent of research.

Figure 3. Personnel (FTE) by category and type of HEI, 2020

Changing roles over time

Between 2000 and 2010 there was an extreme expansion of the Czech higher education system. In the first half of the 1990s the Czech tertiary system was still strictly elite, but over the next 15 years it went through a mass phase to a universal phase. While in 2001 there were about 203,500 students in the Czech higher education system, in 2010 there were about 396,000, which means almost twice as many. At that time, the demand for higher education was created by a higher proportion of applicants over the age of 25 entering higher education for the first time. After 2010, the share of first-time enrolments in tertiary education over the age of 25 declined at virtually the same rate as it grew between 2000 and 2010.

This, combined with demographic developments, has led to a sharp decline in the number of students in tertiary education after 2011: data on student enrolment numbers show a pattern of decrease from 2011 to 2020, with the number of students at Universities decreasing by 24%. From 2019 to 2020, a slight increase of student numbers by 4% might indicate a turnaround with respect to enrolled students at Universities (Figure 4). Similarly, at Non-university type HEIs enrolment decreased by 26% from 2011 to 2020 of the students

enrolled. However, since 2017, the total number of students at Non-university type HEIs remained mostly stable.

Figure 4. Number of students enrolled by type of HEI, 2011-2020

While total student enrolment in Czech HEIs decreased from 2011 to 2020, employment of academic personnel shows a quite different paths (Figure 5). While the number of total academic personnel at University decreased from 2011 to 2014, mainly due to a reduction in 2012, from 2015 onwards we observe an increase of total academic personnel, reaching about 23,500 FTE in 2020. Moreover, only from 2015 onwards, personnel with third-party funding is included. At Non-university type institutions, we see a sharp increase in the number of total academic personnel (FTE) from 2011 to 2015 and levelling off thereafter. Only in the last year of observation, 2020, the number of academic staff at Non-universities drops again by 18%.

Figure 5. Number of students enrolled by type of HEI, 2011-2020

Note: From 2015 onwards, staff data became available for all staff regardless of source of financing; until 2014, only data for staff financed from state budget is included.

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